

CUSTOMER RELATIONSHIP MANAGEMENT, INBOUND MARKETING STRATEGIES, AND SALES PERFORMANCE OF CLEAN ENERGY PROFESSIONALS IN A GLOBAL CONSULTANCY COMPANY

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the impact of *Customer Relationship Management* (CRM) and *inbound marketing* strategies on the sales performance of clean energy professionals within a consultancy company. Utilizing a descriptive correlational design, the research aimed to explore how elements such as pipeline management, quote and order management, *business analytics*, content marketing, lead generation, and social media engagement influenced business outcomes. A validated, adapted questionnaire distributed through Microsoft Forms gathered responses from 120 sales and marketing professionals out of a population of 238. The study employed four-point Likert scales and statistical tools including mean, Independent T-test, and Pearson product-moment correlation coefficient to analyze the data. Results revealed that the Global Consultancy Company demonstrated highly managed CRM practices and extensively applied *inbound marketing* strategies. While CRM elements received high ratings, no significant relationship was found between CRM and sales performance (p-values = .125–.835). Conversely, a significant relationship emerged between *inbound marketing* strategies and sales performance (p-values = .001–.045), highlighting their importance in driving business success. As a result, an action plan was developed to further enhance *inbound marketing* practices, strengthen customer engagement, and support sustainable growth in the highly competitive clean energy sector.

Keywords: *Customer Relationship Management, Inbound Marketing, Sales Performance, Renewable Energy, Business Analytics*

INTRODUCTION

As global demand grows for sustainable energy solutions, the energy sector is undergoing a profound transition fueled by the urgent need to mitigate greenhouse gas emissions, climate change, and environmental degradation. This shift is evident in the rapid adoption of *renewable energy* sources, particularly solar and wind, which are the fastest-growing energy contributors worldwide. According to the International Energy Agency (IEA, 2023), *renewable energy* is expected to account for 30% of global electricity production by 2030. This aligns with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goal 7, which promotes access to affordable, reliable, and modern energy for all (United Nations, 2024).

In line with global priorities, the Philippines has strengthened its clean energy commitment by targeting 35% of its energy mix to be sourced from renewables by 2030. In 2020 alone, the country added 434 megawatts of new solar capacity, contributing significantly to regional energy sustainability (Koty, 2023). The Department of Science and Technology (DOST, 2022) further supports this transition through its Harmonized National Research and Development Agenda, reinforcing policy alignment with the Philippine Development Plan.

In this evolving energy market, organizations like the Global Consultancy Company (GCC) offer specialized services, such as solar PV, green hydrogen, and battery storage systems. Strategically positioned in Taguig City, Philippines, GCC operates in coordination with global offices and integrates *Customer Relationship Management* (CRM) and *Inbound Marketing* Strategies (IMS) to support client acquisition and growth (Clean Energy Associates, 2024). Despite these advancements, challenges in sales pipeline management, conversion, and customer retention remain pervasive in the sector.

CRM functions including pipeline management, quote and order processing, and *business analytics* enable companies to track, personalize, and optimize customer interactions. Prior research emphasizes CRM's ability to enhance client satisfaction and streamline sales processes (Kunzel & Lohse, 2022). Complementing this, IMS emphasizes content marketing, lead nurturing, and social media outreach to build long-term relationships with prospects (HubSpot, 2024). Unlike traditional outbound strategies, *inbound marketing* fosters customer trust through value-driven engagement.

Although assorted studies have explored CRM and IMS in different sectors, few have examined their interrelationship with sales performance within the context of *renewable energy* consulting. This study addresses that gap by evaluating how CRM and IMS influence sales metrics specifically sales revenue and growth among clean energy professionals at GCC. The findings are expected to offer practical insights to strengthen marketing tactics, improve customer engagement, and promote sustainable business performance.

Research Questions

This study examined the relationship between *Customer Relationship Management* (CRM), *Inbound Marketing* Strategies (IMS), and sales performance among clean energy professionals at Global Consultancy Company. Specifically, it sought to answer the following research questions:

1. What is the level of *Customer Relationship Management* (CRM) in Global Consultancy Company as assessed by clean energy professionals in terms of:
 - 1.1 Pipeline Management
 - 1.2 Quote and Order Management
 - 1.3 *Business Analytics*
2. What is the level of *Inbound Marketing* Strategies (IMS) in Global Consultancy Company as assessed by clean energy professionals in terms of:
 - 2.1 Content Marketing
 - 2.2 Lead Generation
 - 2.3 Social Media Engagement
3. What is the level of sales performance of clean energy professionals in Global Consultancy Company in terms of:
 - 3.1 Sales Revenue
 - 3.2 Sales Growth
4. Is there a significant relationship between the level of *Customer Relationship Management* (CRM) and sales performance among clean energy professionals of Global Consultancy Company?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the level of *Inbound Marketing* Strategies (IMS) and sales performance among clean energy professionals of Global Consultancy Company?
6. Based on the findings of the study, what action plan may be proposed to improve sales performance through CRM and IMS?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design This study utilized a quantitative correlational research design to explore the relationships between *Customer Relationship Management* (CRM), *Inbound Marketing* Strategies (IMS), and sales performance among clean energy professionals. A structured survey was used to collect data from participants, with regression and correlational analyses applied to evaluate the strength and direction of relationships between the identified variables.

Research Locale Data collection was conducted remotely through the virtual platforms of the participating organization. Clean energy professionals based in various global locations participated via online surveys, enabling broad representation and geographic diversity in the sample.

Population and Sampling Technique The target population consisted of 238 clean energy professionals. Through random sampling, 120 individuals were selected to

participate, ensuring the generalizability of findings. Participants were primarily from departments directly involved in sales, marketing, project management, and business development.

Respondents of the Study

Category	Frequency	Percent
Sales Representatives	60	50.00%
Business Development Managers/Directors	12	10.00%
Marketing Specialists	24	20.00%
Account/Project Managers	24	20.00%
Total	120	100.00%

Research Instrument A structured questionnaire was used as the main data gathering tool, organized into three sections corresponding to the study’s primary variables: CRM, IMS, and sales performance. The instrument included multiple-choice and four-point Likert scale items. Each section addressed specific sub-variables:

- CRM: Pipeline Management, Quote and Order Management, *Business Analytics*
- IMS: Content Marketing, Lead Generation, Social Media Engagement
- Sales Performance: Sales Revenue, Sales Growth

Validation and Reliability of the Instrument The adapted instrument underwent expert validation by internal reviewers (statistician, research director, faculty member) and external professionals from the target organization. It was pilot tested by 15 sales operations staff. Reliability was confirmed through Cronbach’s Alpha:

- CRM Section: $\alpha = 0.751$
- IMS Section: $\alpha = 0.802$
- Sales Performance Section: $\alpha = 0.814$

These values indicated high internal consistency.

Data-Gathering Procedure The final version of the questionnaire was deployed using Microsoft Forms. It was introduced during a virtual company assembly and distributed via Microsoft Outlook and Teams. The survey was open for five days and designed for completion in approximately six minutes. A total of 120 completed responses were collected and subsequently analyzed using SPSS, with the assistance of a professional statistician.

Statistical Treatment and Analysis The data were processed using the following statistical tools:

- **Mean and Four-Point Likert Scale:** To assess the levels of CRM, IMS, and sales performance.
- **Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Coefficient:** To test the significance of relationships between:
 - CRM and sales performance
 - IMS and sales performance

Scope and Limitations This study focused solely on clean energy professionals within a single consultancy organization. Results may not be generalizable to other industries or organizational settings. Potential limitations include self-reporting bias and reliance on online survey tools, which may affect response accuracy.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Level of Customer Relationship Management in Terms of Pipeline Management Clean energy professionals rated pipeline management practices as Highly Managed, with a general mean of 3.77. The indicator with the highest score (3.83) was the ease of updating project status in the CRM pipeline. In contrast, the lowest (3.71) concerned the CRM system’s use in analyzing sales interactions and identifying trends. This highlights GCC’s efficiency in pipeline operation and user-friendly CRM design but suggests room to enhance its analytical depth.

Table 1.1

Level of Customer Relationship Management in Global Consultancy Company as assessed by Clean Energy Professionals in terms of Pipeline Management

Indicators in terms of Pipeline Management	\bar{X}	VI	Rank
1. The sales pipeline is regularly updated and managed to ensure accurate forecasting and tracking of sales performance.	3.78	SA	4
2. CRM software is utilized to track and analyze sales interactions, leads, and conversions, facilitating the identification of trends and opportunities.	3.71	SA	7
3. The CRM system effectively tracks and manages the sales pipeline for clean energy projects.	3.81	SA	2.5
4. Updating the status of potential projects in the CRM pipeline is straightforward and user-friendly.	3.83	SA	1
5. The CRM provides clear visibility into the various stages of each opportunity within the sales pipeline.	3.74	SA	6

6. The pipeline management features in the CRM assist in prioritizing leads based on their likelihood of conversion.	3.81	SA	2.5
7. The CRM system contributes to the overall efficiency of pipeline management processes within the organization.	3.75	SA	5
General Assessment	3.77	SA	
Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree (SA)/ Highly Managed 2.50 – 3.24 Agree (A)/ Managed 1.75 – 2.49 Disagree (D)/ Slightly Managed 1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree (SD)/ Not Managed			

These findings align with Madruga et al. (2024), who emphasized that combining relationship marketing with personalized communication enhances client retention. Similarly, Rodriguez and Boyer (2020) stressed that mobile CRM tools significantly improve collaboration and sales tracking when integrated with team workflows.

2. Level of CRM in Terms of Quote and Order Management

This area also rated as Highly Managed, with a mean of 3.31. The automation of quote and order handling (3.56) was the highest-rated indicator, while generating quotes for energy solutions (3.13) scored the lowest, suggesting an opportunity to simplify quoting systems.

Table 1.2

Level of *Customer Relationship Management* in Global Consultancy Company as assessed by Clean Energy Professionals in terms of Quote and Order Management

Indicators in terms of Quote and Order Management	\bar{X}	VI	Rank
1. The company’s quote and order management process is automated, allowing for efficient handling of quotes and order acceptance	3.56	SA	1
2. The <i>customer relationship management</i> (CRM) system simplifies the generation of quotes for clean energy solutions.	3.13	A	5
3. The CRM facilitates seamless communication with customers regarding their quotes and orders.	3.17	A	4
4. The CRM solution significantly reduces errors in the quote and order processing.	3.23	A	3
5. Customer feedback regarding quotes and order processes is easily captured and managed within the CRM.	3.48	SA	2

General Assessment	3.31	SA
Legend:	3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree (SA)/ Highly Managed	
	2.50 – 3.24 Agree (A)/ Managed	
	1.75 – 2.49 Disagree (D)/ Slightly Managed	
	1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree (SD)/ Not Managed	

These results resonate with Deloitte Insights (2023) and the IEA (2024), both of which called for technical streamlining to overcome clean energy operational challenges.

3. Level of CRM in Terms of *Business Analytics*

Respondents agreed that CRM’s analytical features are Highly Managed (mean = 3.62). The most praised item was the CRM’s integration of analytics for innovation (3.79), while forecasting data quality had a slightly lower score (3.48).

Table 1.3

Level of *Customer Relationship Management* in Global Consultancy Company as assessed by Clean Energy Professionals in terms of *Business Analytics*

Indicators in terms of <i>Business Analytics</i>	\bar{X}	VI	Rank
1. The company’s <i>customer relationship management</i> (CRM) system provides real-time analytics and insights into customer behavior, preferences, and interactions, enabling data-driven decision-making.	3.67	SA	2.5
2. The analytics capabilities of the CRM system offer valuable insights into customer behavior and trends within the clean energy market.	3.67	SA	2.5
3. <i>Business analytics</i> features of the CRM are regularly utilized to inform decision-making processes.	3.62	SA	4
4. The company effectively identifies new opportunities for growth through analytics derived from the CRM.	3.52	SA	5
5. Reports generated by the CRM provide meaningful data that assists in strategic planning and forecasting.	3.48	SA	6
6. The integration of <i>business analytics</i> tools within the CRM system supports continuous improvement and innovation within the organization.	3.79	SA	1
General Assessment	3.62	SA	
Legend:	3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree (SA)/ Highly Managed		
	2.50 – 3.24 Agree (A)/ Managed		

1.75 – 2.49 Disagree (D)/ Slightly Managed
 1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree (SD)/ Not Managed

This underscores insights from Motyka et al. (2023), emphasizing the growing influence of data analytics in energy investment and infrastructure planning.

4. Level of *Inbound Marketing* in Terms of Content Marketing

Respondents strongly agreed that content strategies are Highly Practiced (mean = 3.61), especially regarding SEO integration (3.72). However, output consistency (3.42) was slightly weaker, suggesting an opportunity to standardize publishing volumes.

Table 2.1

Level of *Inbound Marketing* Strategies in Global Consultancy Company as assessed by Clean Energy Professionals in terms of Content Marketing

Indicators in terms of Content Marketing	\bar{X}	VI	Rank
1. The company creates a minimum of five high-quality, engaging content pieces per month (e.g., blog posts, whitepapers, e-books) to attract and retain customers.	3.42	SA	6
2. Content produced by the company is aligned with the buyer's journey, providing relevant information at each stage of the decision-making process.	3.65	SA	4
3. Educational content generated effectively communicates the benefits of clean energy solutions.	3.68	SA	2.5
4. The educational materials available regarding clean energy initiatives are informative and valuable for enhancing knowledge and performance.	3.53	SA	5
5. Search engine optimization (SEO) practices are integrated into content creation to improve visibility and reach.	3.72	SA	1
6. The company actively promotes its content through various channels, including social media, email newsletters, and partnerships, to maximize reach and impact.	3.68	SA	2.5
General Assessment	3.61	SA	

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree (SA)/ Highly Practiced
 2.50 – 3.24 Agree (A)/ Practiced
 1.75 – 2.49 Disagree (D)/ Slightly Practiced
 1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree (SD)/ Not Practiced

Findings reinforce Webflow (2024) and WordStream (2024), who both highlight SEO integration and content consistency as essential for inbound success.

5. Level of IMS in Terms of Lead Generation

This component is also rated as Highly Practiced (mean = 3.54). The top performer was automation (3.66), while nurturing leads via personalized follow-ups scored lower (3.50).

Table 2.2

Level of *Inbound Marketing* Strategies in Global Consultancy Company as assessed by Clean Energy Professionals in terms of Lead Generation

Indicators in terms of Lead Generation	\bar{X}	VI	Rank
1. The company utilizes a minimum of five lead-generation channels (e.g., website, social media, email, content marketing) to attract and capture leads.	3.57	SA	2
2. A documented lead generation strategy is in place, complete with clear goals and metrics for measuring success.	3.52	SA	3.5
3. Informative lead generation efforts in clean energy foster greater engagement from potential customers.	3.51	SA	5
4. The company employs targeted messaging and campaigns to resonate with diverse audience segments.	3.52	SA	3.5
5. The company effectively utilizes marketing automation tools to streamline lead generation processes.	3.66	SA	1
6. The company actively nurtures leads through personalized communication and follow-up tactics.	3.50	SA	6
General Assessment	3.54	SA	

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree (SA)/ Highly Practiced
 2.50 – 3.24 Agree (A)/ Practiced
 1.75 – 2.49 Disagree (D)/ Slightly Practiced
 1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree (SD)/ Not Practiced

These results validate insights from Dripify (2024) and DataGardener (2024), both of whom stress the importance of humanizing tech-driven lead strategies.

6. Level of IMS in Terms of Social Media Engagement

This was rated Practiced (mean = 3.20). While regular posting was noted positively (3.28), impact on perceived brand expertise was rated lower (3.14).

Table 2.3

Level of *Inbound Marketing Strategies* in Global Consultancy Company as assessed by Clean Energy Professionals in terms of Social Media Engagement

Indicators in terms of Social Media Engagement	\bar{X}	VI	Rank
1. The company has a dedicated social media team responsible for managing its social media presence.	3.18	A	4
2. The organization's social media campaigns positively influence perceptions of its expertise in clean energy.	3.14	A	5
3. Social media posts are regularly updated to reflect current trends and developments in the clean energy industry.	3.28	SA	1
4. The use of visual content (such as images and videos) in social media enhances the effectiveness of communication.	3.19	A	2.5
5. Social media analytics are utilized to evaluate engagement levels and inform future content strategies.	3.19	A	2.5
General Assessment	3.20	A	

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree (SA)/ Highly Practiced
 2.50 – 3.24 Agree (A)/ Practiced
 1.75 – 2.49 Disagree (D)/ Slightly Practiced
 1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree (SD)/ Not Practiced

As suggested by Advertising Week (2024) and Emplifi (2024), further investment in content strategy and visual storytelling can boost GCC’s digital reputation.

7. Sales Performance in Terms of Sales Revenue This was rated Very High (mean = 3.56). Strongest feedback pointed to revenue gains from clean energy services (3.73), with lower scores for customer feedback use (3.43).

Table 3.1

Level of Sales Performance of Clean Energy Professionals in Global Consultancy Company in terms of Sales Revenue

Indicators in terms of Sales Revenue	\bar{X}	VI	Rank
1. The company has experienced a significant increase in sales revenue from clean energy solutions.	3.73	SA	1
2. <i>Inbound marketing</i> strategies have contributed to a noticeable growth in revenue from clean energy services.	3.54	SA	5
3. Data analytics from the CRM system have effectively identified new revenue opportunities within service offerings.	3.56	SA	4
4. Sales revenue growth is regularly tracked and analyzed to inform future business strategies.	3.53	SA	6
5. Customer feedback and market trends are actively utilized to enhance revenue generation efforts.	3.43	SA	8
6. Collaborative efforts between sales and marketing teams have strengthened revenue growth initiatives.	3.52	SA	7
7. The company has successfully expanded its client base in the clean energy sector through targeted strategies.	3.67	SA	3
8. Focus on upselling and cross-selling has proven effective in increasing average revenue per client.	3.38	SA	9
9. Sales performance metrics are regularly reviewed to assess the effectiveness of revenue-generating activities.	3.72	SA	2
General Assessment	3.56	SA	

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree (SA)/ Very High
 2.50 – 3.24 Agree (A)/ High
 1.75 – 2.49 Disagree (D)/ Low
 1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree (SD)/ Very Low

This echoes findings by Medallia (2024) and McKinsey (2024) about the pivotal role of consumer behavior data in boosting revenue strategies.

8. Sales Performance in Terms of Sales Growth

This also scored Very High (mean = 3.63). Marketing’s role in growth (3.85) and client feedback utilization (3.84) was highlights. Campaign evaluation (3.31) was the weakest point.

Table 3.2

Level of Sales Performance of Clean Energy Professionals in Global Consultancy Company in terms of Sales Growth

Indicators in terms of Sales Growth	\bar{X}	VI	Rank
1. The company has achieved a significant increase in its customer base through sales efforts.	3.63	SA	4
2. <i>Inbound marketing</i> strategies have played a crucial role in enhancing the sales growth rate for clean energy services over the past year.	3.85	SA	1
3. Sales growth is consistently monitored to identify trends and inform strategic decisions.	3.52	SA	5
4. The effectiveness of promotional campaigns is regularly evaluated to maximize sales growth opportunities.	3.31	SA	6
5. Feedback from clients is actively utilized to adapt services and enhance sales performance.	3.84	SA	2
6. Training and development initiatives for the sales team have positively impacted overall sales growth.	3.66	SA	3
General Assessment	3.63	SA	

Legend: 3.25 – 4.00 Strongly Agree (SA)/ Very High
 2.50 – 3.24 Agree (A)/ High
 1.75 – 2.49 Disagree (D)/ Low
 1.00 – 1.74 Strongly Disagree (SD)/ Very Low

Salesroom Team (2024) and Schmukler (2024) stressed that continuous evaluation of marketing effectiveness is essential for sustainable growth.

9. Relationship Between CRM and Sales Performance

The Pearson analysis revealed no significant relationship between CRM and sales performance (p-values = .125–.835). This supports Kumari (2022) and Soliman (2021), who noted CRM’s indirect contribution and dependency on external business factors.

Table 4

Test of Significant Relationship between the Level of *Customer Relationship Management* and Sales Performance among Clean Energy Professionals of Global Consultancy Company

Level of Customer Relationship Management	Sales Performance Level	r value	P value	Remarks	Decision
Pipeline Management	Sales Revenue	.053	.563	Not Significant	Accept H _o
	Sales Growth	.027	.768	Not Significant	Accept H _o
Quote and Order Management	Sales Revenue	.141	.125	Not Significant	Accept H _o
	Sales Growth	.028	.763	Not Significant	Accept H _o
<i>Business Analytics</i>	Sales Revenue	.085	.357	Not Significant	Accept H _o
	Sales Growth	.019	.835	Not Significant	Accept H _o

**Correlational at the level 0.01

*Correlational at the level 0.05(Two-tailed)

This suggests that although CRM practices were rated highly by clean energy professionals, they did not directly influence sales performance outcomes within the context of this study. These findings align with those of Kumari (2022), who found that CRM effectiveness in enhancing sales results is context-dependent and moderated by organizational culture, implementation strategy, and employee readiness. Similarly, Soliman (2021) highlighted that CRM's impact is often indirect improving customer satisfaction and operational efficiency without necessarily leading to measurable increases in revenue or growth unless coupled with other strategic factors.

Therefore, while CRM remains a vital organizational tool, its role in driving sales performance at GCC may be more supportive than catalytic. These findings suggest the need to investigate complementary factors such as market dynamics, pricing strategies, or product offerings that may more directly impact sales success in the clean energy consulting space.

10. Relationship Between *Inbound Marketing* and Sales Performance

There was a significant positive relationship between IMS and sales performance (p-values = .001–.045). This means improvements in content marketing, lead generation, and social media positively influence both revenue and growth.

Table 5

Test of Significant Relationship between the Level of *Inbound Marketing* Strategies and the Sales Performance among Clean Energy Professionals of Global Consultancy Company

Level of <i>Inbound Marketing</i> Strategies	Sales Performance Level	r value	P value	Remarks	Decision
Content Marketing	Sales Revenue	.153*	.045	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Sales Growth	.274**	.002	Significant	Reject H ₀
Lead Generation	Sales Revenue	.294**	.001	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Sales Growth	.306**	.001	Significant	Reject H ₀
Social Media Engagement	Sales Revenue	.157*	.037	Significant	Reject H ₀
	Sales Growth	.205*	.025	Significant	Reject H ₀

**Correlational at the level 0.01

*Correlational at the level 0.05(Two-tailed)

These findings echo FinancesOnline (2024) and Qwilr (2024), who found that *inbound marketing* yields more high-quality leads and lower acquisition costs.

11. Action Plan An action plan was developed to enhance CRM systems, improve quote/order handling, optimize social media, and boost sales through targeted campaigns, webinars, and automation strategies.

Table 6

Proposed Action Plan: Enhancing CRM, *Inbound Marketing*, and Sales Performance

Key Areas	Objectives	Strategies/Activities	Time Frame	Persons Involved	Source of Fund	Success Indicators
CRM Enhancement	Improve Quote and Order Management	Implement an advanced CRM system for better quote and order tracking	Q1 2025	IT and Sales Teams	IT Budget	Reduced order processing time (70%)
		Conduct training sessions on new CRM features	Q1-Q2 2025	External CRM Experts	Training Budget	Higher user adoption rate (85%)
		Automate quote generation and approval processes	Q2 2025	IT and Sales Teams	IT Budget	Increased quote accuracy, faster approvals (80%)
<i>Inbound Marketing</i> Optimization	Enhance Social Media	Increase budget for social media advertising	Q1 2025	Marketing Team	Marketing Budget	Higher engagement rates,

Key Areas	Objectives	Strategies/Activities	Time Frame	Persons Involved	Source of Fund	Success Indicators
	Engagement					improved reach (85%)
		Develop a social media content calendar for consistent posting	Q1 2025	Social Media Team	Marketing Budget	Consistent content output, higher audience retention (90%)
		Collaborate with social media influencers to boost engagement	Q2-Q3 2025	PR and Marketing Teams	Marketing Budget	Increased brand awareness, higher engagement (75%)
		Utilize video marketing to create engaging content for social media platforms	Q1-Q4 2025	Marketing Team	Marketing Budget	Increased video views, higher social media engagement (85%)
Sales Performance Improvement	Increase Sales Revenue	Launch targeted promotional campaigns for clean energy solutions	Q2-Q4 2025	Sales and Marketing Team	Sales Budget	Increased sales revenue, higher market share (75%)
		Utilize marketing automation tools to streamline lead generation and follow-up	Ongoing	IT and Sales Teams	IT Budget	More efficient lead management, higher conversion rates (80%)
		Develop personalized email marketing campaigns to nurture leads	Q1-Q3 2025	Marketing Team	Marketing Budget	Higher lead conversion rates, increased customer loyalty (85%)
		Host webinars and virtual events to showcase clean energy solutions	Q2-Q4 2025	Sales and Marketing Team	Sales Budget	Increased lead generation, higher attendee engagement (80%)

Based on the findings, an action plan was developed to address identified areas for improvement and to sustain high-performing practices. The key priorities included optimizing CRM tools especially in quote and order management, enhancing *inbound*

marketing efforts with a focus on content output and social media engagement, and boosting sales revenue through strategic campaigns and lead nurturing.

For CRM, the action plan emphasized system upgrades, automation of quoting processes, and comprehensive training for team adoption. These strategies aim to reduce manual tasks, increase accuracy, and elevate user efficiency. This aligns with findings from Guzenko (2024), which emphasized the importance of seamless CRM integration to improve operational workflows in energy markets.

On the *inbound marketing* front, the plan proposed using visual content, influencer collaborations, and consistent scheduling through a content calendar. These steps reflect recommendations from Emplifi (2024) and Webflow (2024), who highlight the growing importance of engaging digital content and brand positioning across platforms.

Sales performance improvements were addressed by combining promotional campaigns, webinars, and marketing automation tools to increase both reach and conversion efficiency. As highlighted by Qwilr (2024) and Dripify (2024), such integrated strategies enhance customer acquisition, loyalty, and sales productivity.

In essence, the action plan serves not only as a response to the study's findings but as a roadmap for achieving long-term growth and competitive advantage in the clean energy consulting sector. Its strength lies in blending data-driven decisions with proactive strategy execution ensuring that CRM, IMS, and sales performance evolve in tandem.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of this study, the following conclusions are drawn:

1. Pipeline management, quote and order management, and *business analytics* under CRM were all assessed as highly effective by clean energy professionals. These areas serve as pillars of customer interaction and internal sales operations and should be sustained to maintain organizational strength.

2. Inbound marketing strategies, particularly content marketing and lead generation were highly practiced and well-received. However, social media engagement scored relatively lower, highlighting a strategic area for enhancement.

3. Sales performance in terms of both sales revenue and sales growth was perceived as very high. This reflects the effectiveness of current sales strategies and underlines the organization's strong market presence and lead-to-revenue conversion practices.

4. No statistically significant relationship was found between CRM and sales performance, suggesting that while CRM supports operations and customer satisfaction, it may not be a direct contributor to increased revenue or growth in this context.

5. A statistically significant relationship existed between *inbound marketing* strategies and sales performance. This indicates that content-driven, customer-centric marketing

efforts are positively influencing both sales revenue and growth, validating the impact of IMS on bottom-line performance.

6. An action plan was designed to address opportunities identified in the study, including improvements to CRM automation, social media strategy, and campaign tracking. This action plan aims to reinforce the company's marketing and sales functions to ensure continued growth and market relevance.

Recommendations

1. Sustain and enhance pipeline, quote, and order management processes through advanced CRM tools and team training. This will ensure efficiency and maintain customer satisfaction levels.

2. Allocate greater focus and resources to social media engagement. Tactics may include influencer partnerships, stronger visual storytelling, and analytics-informed campaign design.

3. Continue leveraging *inbound marketing* techniques by maintaining high-quality content production and refining lead-nurturing practices. Emphasis should be placed on SEO, consistency, and personalized communication.

4. Integrate customer feedback and market analysis more deeply into sales strategy planning. Doing so could boost revenue impact and capitalize on changing consumer preferences.

5. Maintain the use of sales performance data as a feedback loop for marketing efforts. Strengthening the alignment between sales insights and marketing direction will support campaign effectiveness.

6. Implement and monitor the proposed action plan to institutionalize continuous improvement. Track progress through key performance indicators, ensuring accountability and adaptability in execution.

7. Future researchers are encouraged to explore related variables such as employee productivity, organizational culture, and external market forces, which may mediate the relationship between CRM, IMS, and sales performance outcomes.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher affirms that this research was conducted with a strong commitment to ethical standards. Participation in the study was entirely voluntary, and informed consent was secured from all respondents. They were also assured that they could withdraw from the study at any time, with no repercussions. The confidentiality and anonymity of their responses were strictly upheld, and all data were handled in accordance with data privacy laws. The well-being of all participants was respected at every stage. There were no conflicts of interest throughout the duration of this research, and great care was taken to avoid any form of plagiarism. The interpretation of findings

was done objectively, without bias, and the insights gained were used solely for academic and research purposes. For full transparency, this paper was developed with the assistance of Microsoft Copilot, an AI-powered writing and research tool which helped refine the writing without compromising the integrity or originality of the ideas presented.

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